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Script, Language and Writing Technics of Manuscript Tradition in Kerala

Dr. Manju P.M¹

The thirst of knowledge has passed down from generation to generation through oral and written documents. Palm leaves, Birch bark, Copper plates, stones, parchments and paper etc. are the writing materials commonly used in Kerala for the preservation and recording of different knowledge system in Sanskrit. These written documents are known as manuscripts. It spread in different institutions, libraries, monasteries, temples, and in several private collections. The subject matter of Manuscripts is Vedas, Upaniṣads, Puranas, Dharmasastras, Itihasas, Darsanas, Tantras, Ayurveda etc. They are sources of cultural heritage and history.

The word manuscript is derived from the Medieval Latin term Manuscriptum that means hand written documents; it means manually recorded books or literary works. The study of Manuscriptology means science of manuscripts; it gives supreme importance to editing the manuscript works. There are another two types of writing methods 1. Lithography, and 2. Xylography. Lithography means writing on stone block and Xylography is writing on wooden block. Both these writing methods can be regarded as manuscripts also. The study of written matter recorded on rocks, pillars, walls of ancient buildings, utensils, bones, and metal plates are known as Epigraphy. The study of ancient scripts is not part of Manuscriptology, it is known as paleography which means the study of ancient writing systems and the deciphering and dating of historical manuscripts. Study of ancient scripts means studying

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origin and development of hieroglyphic and phonetic symbols.

Palm leaf Manuscript in Kerala

In Kerala, there are two types of palm leaf manuscripts used for written documents. 1. *Borassus flabellifer* (Sugar palm). 2. *Corypha umbraculifera* (Talipot palm). A single rectangular palm leaflet is known as Taliyola in Malayalam language, which means the leaf of anyone of the above palms. A Manuscript contains a number of rectangular folios or Taliolas, threaded at each end by a country string. Talipot palm lasts longer than Sugar palm as the former is more durable. Therefore, the most surviving ancient texts are written in the leaves of Talipot palm in Kerala mostly.

Various categories of palm leaf Manuscript in Kerala

Various categories of palm leaf manuscripts were used in ancient times in Kerala for these kinds of writing purpose. They are Chūr, a, Grantha and Ozhuḥku. Chūr, a is loose sheets of palm sizes after passing a country cord through the holes made in the leaves. The number of sheets in each bundle varies from 500-1000. Chūr, a bundles mostly deal with different types of accounts of families or land properties. Nowadays they can be seen preserved in the Archives Centre Thiruvananthapuram and Archives centre, Trippunithura etc. A collection of palm leaf manuscripts preserved with in wooden flaps is known as Grantha. In most cases it is a granary of literary collection such as Rāmāya, a, Mahābhārata, Bhāgavata, Bhagavatgīta, and Hymns of lord āiva, Kriṣ, a etc. the historical records are also kept as Granthas in many places. The minute details of land properties including survey number, taxes, area, categories etc. are seen in recorded in manuscript which is known as Ozhuḥku. Both sides of the record consist of details regarding the description of the land, signatures of the grantor, witnesses, state administrator etc.

Scripts and languages of manuscripts in Kerala

The development of scripts and language is in variably interconnected. Scripts like Brāhmi, Kharoṣṭhi, Grantha, Vaṭṭtzhuttu, Kolezhuttu, Tulu or Ēryazhuttu, Malayālam and Devanāgarī etc. are the tool for expressing human being's ideas through their own languages. The Brāhmi script is the parent of several families and sub-families of scripts developed in North and South India and in

South Asia, Tibet, Nepal and Srilanka.

It is generally accepted that the scripts of Malayālam language got their final form at the time Thuncattezuttaccan, the father of Malayālam language and literature who is the author of Adhyātmarāmāya, am, Devīmāhātmyam etc. the script of that time was adapted for printing Malayalam later in 1836 (Jagannathan).

Dr. S.Jagannathan said that the Grantha script originated from the Brāhmi which are found in some caves in Tamil Nadu. Sri. Sivaramamurthy suggests that the script evolved from Maurya Satavahana- Ikshvaku - early Pallava writings and Bhatti Prolu - Tamil caves. Vedic scholars in Tamil Nadu still use the Grantha script to write Sanskrit.

During the Pandyakings and Vijayanagara period, there existed two types of Grantha script, eastern and western. Eastern Grantha script is found around Tanjavore, Madurai and Arcot regions and western Grantha script which later on came to be known as Tulu Malayalam script, in the Malabar region of Kerala and adjoining west coast regions of Karnataka. Vaṭṭezhuttu has really developed from the Brāhmi script found in the caves in Tamil Nadu. The earliest documents in Malayalam are found in vaṭṭezhuttu script which was originally used for writing Tamil in Pandyan and Chera territories. Kolezhuttu is a writing system that evolved from Vaṭṭezhuttu, was also used for writing Malayalam at least from the 10th C.A.D. onwards. Vaṭṭezhuttu was the script of Tamil Language prevailing in the region of Tamilakam (the entire part of Kerala- Cera and Pandya region and major part of Tamil Nadu, thus Vaṭṭezhuttu, Kolezhuttu and Aryezhuttu were used for writing Malayalam Language also in early times. At that time Malayalam was known under various names, Malayālma, Malayānma and Malayāyma. Some scholars agree that it may be conclusively stated that Malayalam and Malayānma were local names for Kolezhuttu in Kerala(Jagannathan).

A.R. Raja Raja Varma, in his famous Grammar book 'Kerala Paanineeyam', opines that the word 'Malayānma' was used to represent the language of 'Malayāla Nādu' (Kerala). He called the period between AD 1325 to AD 1625 as 'Malayānma Kālam' (the age of Malayānma), the period when there was tremendous progress in the language. He also assumes that the Tamil spoken in Kerala

was termed as 'Malayām Tamil' and this was reduced to 'Malayānma' (Salsanath S.N and Kunjamma).

After the development stage of Malayālam language, the flourishing Sanskrit literacy produced a mixed language called Manipravālam. A considerable number of works styled as Manipravālam are available in the medieval literature in Kerala.

Traditional method of preservation of manuscript in Kerala.

Neem leaves, dried turmeric, Turmeric powder, Karpūram and Tulasi etc. are the materials used for preserving the manuscripts in traditional manner in Kerala. Palm leaf manuscripts were preserved in the loft of the kitchen for driving away the insects and fungi from them and to make them more hard and strong. Another way of preservation in Kerala is to wrap them in red cloth and keep in a wooden box. Nowadays the preservation of manuscript's method has advanced very much using new techniques, materials and instruments.

Writing Technics in Manuscript

In writing Manuscripts scribes use Nārāyam or Ezhutta,ⁱ for writing and using certain technics which are as follows:

Lines: the scribe use temporarily lines that can be erased later for maintaining level of lines in Manuscript. Charcoal, Pencil etc. are materials used for their purpose.

Combination of letters and words: usually, scribes do not make paragraphs or other methods for separating ālokas or lines or sections in the textual mater. All the texts written in continuous set of lines. Paragraph is not indicated even at the end of the chapters. In most of the Manuscripts, some designs are drawn in left margin against the exact level of the line or at the end line; it indicates the chapter is being concluded. For example sign of Puṣpa(flower) is used in manuscripts in such cases.

Punctuation Marks are considered, the end of a word or a sentence and it also separates Gadya from Padya each other. Daṇḍa (vertical line) is an example. Sometimes double vertical lines are also used for the same purpose.

Pagination: two unique methods for indicating numbers of pages are found in Kerala Manuscripts. 1. KAṬAPAYĒDI system. In this scheme some numbers are given to the Malayalam alphabets

like Ka, Ca, Ṭa, Ta Pa and bigger numbers are formed by combing such letter in a particular way. For example Ka, Ṭa, Pa and ya indicate number -1. Whereas Kha Tha , Pha and ra indicates number – this system is very popular in Kerala. 2. NANNANYADI system. In this scheme na indicate number – 1 NNA indicates number -2 and nya indicates number -3. In this manner formation of small and big numbers can be done according to this scheme also. Malayalam script is used this method commonly.

Symbols denoting letters or Portions left while writing: one example this is a symbol that denotes that a letter is left while writing the manuscript. In such cases, the letter will be shown above the symbol in between the lines.

Error : in the content of the manuscript, the scribes make small horizontal lines in the bottom or top of the letters or words for denoting that there is some error in writing in that line. Sometimes such portions are denoted by smearing turmeric powder also. 1. Lopa (Omission) 2. Ēgama (augment or addition) 3. Ēdesa (change or substitute) etc. are also denoted sometimes by such symbols.

Auspicious words and symbols: Auspicious words or expressions like Hari ārī Ga, apataye Namah, Svasti are seen used in almost all Manuscript in Kerala in the beginning. In the same way the word or expression Hari is found given in the end of the manuscript also. The auspicious beginning and end is often denoted by the symbol like Svasti also in manuscript.

Colophon: Scribes usually add a concluding note for information about the title; date and place of works etc. as colophon in manuscript. These are very helpful for understanding the title and contents of the works definitely.

Chronogram: is encoding particular date in letter or in words form in a manuscript that denotes the date of the work or the date of its transcription. Such dates are indicated by the Kaṭapayāti or Nannanyādi system as referred to above.

Flyleaf: At the beginning and end of the manuscript, one or more extra blank leaves are often used which are called flyleaf.

Illumination: is Gold and Silver are sometimes used for decorating

manuscripts. The manuscripts decorated in other colors without the gold or silver are also found commonly.

Marginalia: the scribe use margin for comments, explanations, clarifications and glosses which are known as Marginalia. They are very helpful for editing the manuscripts.

Manuscript repositories in Kerala

Government and private repositories of manuscripts are exists in Kerala. The following names of libraries which are among them:

- Ayurveda College, Thiruvananthapuram.
- Govt. Ayurveda College, Thrippunithura
- Vaidyaratnam Ayurveda College, Thaikkattusery, Ollur, Thrissur.
- Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier Ayurveda College, Kottakkal, Malappuram.
- Govt. Ayurveda College, Pariyaram, Kannur.
- Naduvil Matham , Trissur.
- Vadamakke swamiyar Matham, Thrissur.
- Madhavannamboothiri Vailisseri Mana, Cheruthuruthi, Thrissur.
- Govt.Sanskrit College Thrippunithura, Ernakulam.
- ORI Manuscript Library, Thiruvananthapuram.

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Salsanath S.N, and Dr. S Kunjamma. "Scripts Used in Ozhuku (Land Records)." Language in India, vol. 23, no. 3, 2023, www.languageinindia.com/march2023/salsanathozhukuscriptsfinal.pdf. Accessed 26 Dec. 2023.